

Supplementary Material

Taxon Sampling and Species Identification

All individuals were collected by hand and transported live to the lab or nightly lodging for processing. Most sampling occurred during multiple trips to the field in 2016-2017, but some specimens were collected prior to 2016 as a part of previous survey work. Snails were collected by hand and preserved following Fukuda et al. (2008). Specimens were fixed in 96-100% ethanol until tissue clips could be taken. Tissue clips were taken in the lab and placed directly into digestion buffer for DNA extractions or placed in cryopreservation vials filled with 96-100% ethanol and stored at -80°C until extraction. All sequenced individuals were photographed and rendered in Adobe Photoshop; minor adjustments to contrast and brightness were made for a small number of shells.

Below are identification notes for select taxa. See the main text for more details

Lithasia fuliginosa: Burch and Tottenham (1980) considered *Li. fuliginosa* to be a subspecies of *Li. geniculata* so *Li. fuliginosa* was not included in the Johnson et al. (2013) list. However, the two vary considerably in shell morphology and ASTRAL analyses recovered *Li. fuliginosa* from the Duck River drainage near the type locality (USNM 1597765, USNM 1597783) as reciprocally monophyletic or as more closely related to *Li. duttoniana* (USNM 1597946, USNM 1597765, USNM 1597782) depending on the dataset analyzed. Thus, we recognize *Li. fuliginosa* as a valid species.

In general, *Lithasia* spp. with smooth shells would be considered to represent *Lithasia fuliginosa*, but *Li. fuliginosa* s.l. was recovered as polyphyletic, denoted here as "*Lithasia* aff. *fuliginosa* from East Fork Stones River" (USNM 1597766) and "*Lithasia* aff. *fuliginosa* from Harpeth River" (USNM 1597769, USNM 1597771). Greater geographic sampling is needed to clarify the ranges and validity of these lineages.

Lithasia jayana: This species was considered extinct by Johnson et al. (2013), but two individuals (USNM 1638599, USNM 1638560) from near its type locality, "Caney Fork" possessed the characteristic double rows of tubercles on the body whorl that define *Li. jayana*. One individual from the Duck River with a faint second tubercle row was initially identified as *Li. jayana* (1597782) based on two rows of tubercles, but we later identified it as *Li. duttoniana* in light of phylogenetic results.

Elimia annettae*, *E. showalteri*, and *E. olivula: Cahaba River drainage *Elimia* are difficult to identify, particularly in the field. Two individuals that we first identified as *E. clara* (USNM 1597595, USNM 1597942) were not reciprocally monophyletic; one individual (USNM 1597942) was recovered closely related to *E. annettae* and the other individual (USNM 1597595) was closely related to *E. showalteri*, and the identifications were changed accordingly. However, *E. clara* may still be a valid species as more extensive sampling in the Cahaba River was outside the scope of this study. Two specimens from the Cahaba River (USNM 1597652, USNM 1597653) were morphologically similar to the type specimen of *Melania olivula* Conrad, 1834 and were identified as *E. olivula*. One individual also classified here as *E. olivula* (USNM 1597700) bears some resemblance to both *E. showalteri* and *E. olivula*, and this specimen was classified as *E. olivula* based on phylogenetic results. Considerable taxonomic work is needed to clarify taxonomic boundaries and determine species-specific shell characters of Cahaba River drainage *Elimia*.

Elimia glarea: Individuals identified as *E. glarea* (USNM 1597613, USNM 1597614) had shell features similar to both *E. glarea* and *E. dooleyensis*. We consider individuals collected here as *E. glarea* because

47 they are from the same drainage as the type locality of *Elimia glarea* Mihalcik and Thompson, 2003 at
48 Blue Springs, Alabama.

49
50 ***Elimia* sp. from the Sipsey River:** These individuals bear some resemblance to *E. hydeii*, but *E. hydeii* was
51 not previously recorded from the Sipsey River. Increased taxon sampling, and possibly anatomical
52 analyses, will be needed to determine if individuals collected here represent a different nominal species,
53 an undescribed species, or a range extension of *E. hydeii*.

54
55 ***Pleurocera alveare*:** Individuals identified as *P. alveare* from two locations, Sequatchie River (USNM
56 1597855, USNM 1597856) and Red River (USNM 1597858, USNM 1597859), were each reciprocally
57 monophyletic. Specimens from each location also had some locality-specific shell differences in shape
58 and ornamentation of body whorl. We treat individuals from the Sequatchie River as *P. alveare* and
59 individuals from the Red River as *P. aff. alveare* because the Sequatchie River is closer to the type
60 locality of *Melania alveare* Conrad, 1834, “Elk River, Alabama”. More extensive geographic sampling,
61 including from the type locality, will be required to determine if multiple species exist within what is
62 currently recognized as *P. alveare*.

63
64 ***Elimia pybasii*:** The two specimens from Big Swann Creek (USNM 1597667, USNM 1597668) are
65 morphologically similar to the type specimen of *Goniobasis pybasii* I. Lea, 1862. Given similarity to the
66 type specimen and because the type locality, “Tuscumbia, Alabama” and Big Swann Creek are both from
67 the Tennessee River drainage, we identified our specimens as *E. pybasii*. These individuals also are
68 similar to *E. laqueata*, but the latter is considered native to the Cumberland River drainage. Additional
69 sampling will be required to clarify the validity and geographic ranges of the two.

70
71 ***Elimia interveniens*:** Two specimens from Limestone Creek (USNM 1597715, USNM 1597717) are similar
72 to the type of *Goniobasis interveniens* I. Lea, 1862 and are consistent with the vague type locality in
73 “Northern Alabama”. Two individuals from the Duck River drainage (USNM 1597718, EsDR10) were
74 closely related and morphologically similar to *E. interveniens* from Limestone Creek and consider them
75 conspecific despite the fact that the species was not previously considered to occur in the Duck River
76 drainage.

77
78 ***Elimia* sp. from the Green River:** We are unaware of any currently recognized species that has a shell
79 morphology that matches specimens collected from the Green River, but they clearly fit the current
80 concept of *Elimia*. Greater geographic sampling to determine the range of this species and thorough
81 analysis of relevant type material to ensure it has not been previously described will be necessary before
82 formal description.

83
84 ***Pleurocera* sp. from the Harpeth, Duck, and Buffalo Rivers:** Three putative species from these rivers are
85 closely related but have notably distinct shell morphologies, particularly in the height of the spire. Thus,
86 we consider them distinct, but we cannot completely rule out that they are conspecific. The nominal
87 species group name, *Melania filum* I. Lea, 1845, may be available for one of these lineages, which has
88 been considered to be a subspecies of *Pleurocera canaliculata* (Burch & Tottenham, 1980). However,
89 unlike *Lithasia fuliginosa*, which was considered a subspecies of *Li. geniculata* by Burch and Tottenham
90 (1980), there are no clear morphological features that distinguish *Pleurocera* sp. from the Harpeth,
91 Duck, and Buffalo Rivers from *P. canaliculata*. Thus, we refrain from placing a species name on these
92 lineages at this time.

93

94 ***Pleurocera prasinata***: The single *Pleurocera* species known from the Cahaba River drainage above the
95 fall line in Alabama is currently recognized as *P. prasinata* (Burch & Tottenham, 1980; Johnson et al.,
96 2013; Whelan & Strong, 2016). However, individuals from the Cahaba River were not reciprocally
97 monophyletic with *P. prasinata* from the type locality, “Alabama River at Claiborne” and from the Coosa
98 River drainage. For this reason, individuals from the Cahaba River are considered *P. aff. prasinata*, rather
99 than *P. prasinata*.

100

101 ***Pleurocera aff. acuta***: *Pleurocera acuta* is currently recognized as a morphologically variable and widely
102 distributed species from Missouri to New York (Burch & Tottenham, 1980). We initially identified
103 specimens as *Pleurocera acuta* following Burch and Tottenham (1980). However, some phylogenetic
104 analyses suggested there were up to three lineages within this species. Unfortunately, we were unable
105 to sample *P. acuta* from the type locality, Lake Erie, so we cannot conclude which lineage, if any, is true
106 *P. acuta*. For this reason, we designate all three lineages as *P. aff. acuta*, acknowledging potential cryptic
107 diversity within the current concept of *P. acuta*.

108

109 ***Leptoxis dilatata***: This species was previously considered endemic to the Kanawha River drainage in
110 West Virginia, a tributary to the Ohio River (Burch & Tottenham, 1980; Goodrich, 1940). However,
111 previous collections of specimens with the distinctive flap-like extension of the ocular peduncle of *L.*
112 *dilatata* and *L. carinata* (see main text) indicated that *L. dilatata* may also be in the North Fork of the
113 Holston River (Whelan et al. *unpublished data*). We initially identified one individual from the *L. dilatata*
114 type locality, Indian Creek in West Virginia, and two individuals from North Fork of the Holston River as
115 *L. dilatata*. Phylogenetic analyses indicated that one individual from the North Fork of the Holston River
116 initially identified as *L. dilatata* was actually *L. subglobosa* (USNM 1638595), but the other individual
117 (USNM 1638594) was closely related to *L. dilatata* from its type locality (USNM 1638594). Based on shell
118 morphology, we recognized the individual from North Fork of the Holston River as *L. dilatata*, but
119 greater geographic sampling is needed to determine if Tennessee River drainage individuals are a
120 distinct species.

121

122 ***Leptoxis subglobosa***: Although *L. subglobosa* is considered a synonym of *L. praerosa* (Burch &
123 Tottenham, 1980), *L. subglobosa* was recognized as valid by Whelan et al. (2015). Furthermore, *Leptoxis*
124 *subglobosa* is morphologically distinguishable from *L. praerosa* based on a more globose body whorl and
125 generally more ovate aperture. Specimens collected from the type locality of *L. subglobosa* (USNM,
126 1638606, USNM 1638605, USNM 1638595), North Fork of the Holston River, and elsewhere (USNM
127 1597835) were recovered reciprocally monophyletic, and not sister to, *L. praerosa*. Therefore, we
128 recognize *L. subglobosa* as a valid species.

129

130 ***Leptoxis praerosa***: *Leptoxis praerosa* is a wide-ranging species in the Tennessee, Cumberland, and Ohio
131 River drainages with some differences in aperture shape and body whorl height across its range.
132 Phylogenetic analyses indicated the presence of three lineages, but additional taxon sampling from type
133 localities of nominal species in synonymy with *L. praerosa* and from more locations in the lower
134 Tennessee, Cumberland, and Ohio River drainages will be necessary before geographic ranges and
135 taxonomic boundaries can be resolved. We consider the specimen from closest to the type locality to be
136 *L. praerosa* (USNM 1638604), whereas the other lineages are denoted as “*L. aff. praerosa* Duck and
137 Harpeth Rivers” (USNM 1597805, USNM 1597800, USNM 1597821) and “*L. aff. praerosa* Limestone
138 Creek” (USNM 1597807).

139

140 ***Elimia simplex***: Specimens collected from Little Sycamore Creek and Duck Creek, both Clinch River
141 tributaries, were identified as *E. simplex*. However, phylogenetic analyses revealed that the two sites

142 represented distinct lineages. We consider specimens from Little Sycamore Creek (USNM 1597710,
 143 USNM 1597711) to be *E. simplex* because they most closely resemble the type. Specimens from Duck
 144 Creek (USNM 1638579, USNM 1638580) are denoted as *E. aff. simplex*. Sampling from the *E. simplex*
 145 type locality in the North Fork of the Holston River drainage near Abingdon, Virginia, will be necessary to
 146 confirm the identity.

147
 148 ***Elimia* sp. Richland Creek:** Specimens collected from Richland Creek (USNM 1638584, USNM 1638585),
 149 a tributary to the Nolichucky River, have no known available name.

150
 151 **Pleuroceridae sp.:** Specimens identified as “Pleuroceridae sp.” have a large ovate aperture, reduced
 152 spire, and a relatively thin shell. Both individuals were collected from the Collins River (USNM 1638603,
 153 USNM 1597935). The inflated body whorl is characteristic of *Leptoxis*, but we are not aware of any
 154 *Leptoxis* records from the Collins River.

155
 156 ***Elimia carinifera*:** This spring-associated species occurs in the Mobile River basin and the Tennessee
 157 River drainage tributaries adjacent to the Coosa River in northeastern Alabama, northwestern Georgia
 158 and southeast Tennessee. It is characterized by the interrupted carinae and by beaded striae on upper
 159 whorls. Initially, specimens from Crawfish Springs (Tennessee River drainage; USNM 159577),
 160 Tapawingo Spring (Black Warrior River drainage, Mobile River basin; USNM 1597940, USNM 1597941),
 161 and Spring Creek (Coosa River drainage, Mobile River basin; USNM 1597581) were all identified as “*E.*
 162 *carinifera*” based on shell morphology. However, phylogenetic results recovered the Tapawingo Spring
 163 specimen as distantly related. Crawfish Springs and Spring Creek are located closer to the type locality
 164 than Tapawingo Spring, so the two closely related individuals from Spring Creek and Crawfish Springs
 165 are considered to be *E. carinifera* and the individual from Tapawingo Spring is denoted as “*E. aff.*
 166 *carinifera*”.

167 168 **Molecular data generation and dataset assembly**

169 170 *Leptoxis ampla* genome sequencing

171 A previously unpublished draft genome of *L. ampla* was used to aid in AHE probe design. Two *L.*
 172 *ampla* individuals were collected in September 2014 from the Cahaba River at US Highway 82
 173 (32.9578°N, 87.1397°W). DNA was extracted with the Qiagen DNeasy Plant Kit as described in the main
 174 text. Whole genomic DNA was shipped to the Genome Services Lab at Hudson Alpha Institute
 175 (Huntsville, Alabama) for library prep and sequencing on an Illumina sequencer. Three Illumina libraries
 176 were prepared: 1) a standard paired-end library with an average insert size of 227 bp, 2) a large insert
 177 paired-end library with an average insert size of 423 base pairs, and 3) a Nextera mate-pair library size
 178 selected for inserts between 3,000 and 5,000 base pairs. Each library was sequenced on a HiSeq 2000
 179 lane with 2x100 paired end chemistry.

180 Raw genomic data were quality checked with the FAST-X toolkit (Gordon 2011), and adapters
 181 were trimmed with Skewer (Jiang et al. 2014). Assembly was done using SOAPdenovo2. Raw data were
 182 prepared for assembly using the SOAPdenovo2 packaged programs Corrector_HA and KmerFreq_HA.
 183 Assembly was done with default parameters and a kmer size of 31; initial assembly was done with the
 184 two paired-end libraries, and all three libraries were used in the scaffolding steps. After assembly
 185 GapCloser v1.12, which is part of SOAPdenovo2, and GapFiller (Boetzer and Pirovano 2012) were used
 186 with default parameters to close assembly gaps in the scaffolds output of SOAPdenovo2. Raw sequence
 187 data are available from the NCBI Short Read Archive [to be provided upon acceptance] and the assembly
 188 is available on FigShare [private link for reviewers: <https://figshare.com/s/8d6e550fd989de95322e>].

189

190 *AHE marker design*

191 As stated in the main text, marker design followed Breinholt et al. (2018). Briefly, potential loci
192 that would be useful for pleurocerid phylogenomics were screened from the *B. glabrata* genome with
193 single copy and orthology criteria from Breinholt et al. (2018). These Potential loci were extracted from
194 pleurocerid transcriptomes and the *L. ampla* genome with the genome_getprobe_BLAST.py script from
195 Espeland et al. (2018). Mitochondrial genes were excluded. Following Breinholt et al. (2018), loci were
196 screened for orthology with s_hit_checker.py and ortholog_filter.py. To be chosen for downstream
197 analyses, loci had to be present in at least 4 of 5 pleurocerid transcriptomes and be over 120 bp in
198 length. For the 742 loci that passed all screens, probes of 120bp were tiled across target regions of each
199 reference taxon at 2X coverage. SureSelect Custom DNA Target Enrichment probes were ordered from
200 Agilent Technologies for use in AHE sequencing.

201

202 *Anchored hybrid enrichment sequencing and data assembly*

203 Library prep was done by first shearing DNA to an average length of 300bp. Sheared DNA was
204 subjected to an end-repair reaction with ligation of an adenine residue to the 3'-end of fragments.
205 Subsequently, unique barcodes and Illumina adaptors were ligated to libraries and amplified with PCR.
206 SureSelect^{XT} Target Enrichment System for Illumina Paired-End Multiplexed Sequencing Libraries and the
207 probe set developed here were used on libraries that were pooled into groups of 16 samples. Paired-
208 end sequencing was done on an Illumina HiSeq 3000 using 2 x 100bp chemistry.

209 Raw data were quality filtered and adaptor sequences were trimmed using Trim Galore! 0.4.4
210 (<https://github.com/FelixKrueger/TrimGalore>) with a quality score cutoff of 20 and a minimum
211 sequence length of 30 bp. Quality trimmed data were assembled for each taxon using an iterative bait
212 assembly process with the IBA.py script from Breinholt et al. (2018). USEARCH v11.0.667 selected raw
213 reads with high similarity to the probe regions from reference taxa and a *de novo* assembly was
214 subsequently built with Bridger 2014-12-01 (Chang et al., 2015) for each taxon. The Bridger assembly for
215 each taxon was done with a paired-end gap length of 200, a kmer length of 25, and a minimum kmer
216 coverage of 10. The *de novo* assembly was then used in subsequent iterations of the iterative bait
217 assembly process to extend sequences outside the probe region. For each taxon, a minimum of six bait
218 assembly iterations were performed.

219 After assembly, loci were processed using a modified version of the AHE processing pipeline
220 from Breinholt et al. (2018). Loci were aligned with mafft (Katoh & Standley, 2013) using the flags --
221 adjustdirectionaccurately to account for sequencing in both directions and ---addlong to handle
222 sequences that flanked the probe/reference sequences. Alignments were split into three regions, the
223 probe region and the two flanking regions. The head and tail flanking sequences corresponded to
224 sequences on the 5' and 3' end of the probe sequence, respectively.

225 Orthology determination was performed on sequences trimmed to the probe region. First, we
226 used tblastx (Camacho et al., 2009) to map sequences to the *B. glabrata* genome; a maximum of three
227 target hits and three hits per target were allowed. Bit scores of blast hits for each sequence were
228 compared and any hit with bit scores within 90% of the best bit score was considered too close to
229 differentiate as a single-copy ortholog and was removed. Retained sequences were again analyzed with
230 tblastx as before, but only one max target hit and one hit per target were allowed. Finally, any single hit
231 sequence that mapped to a different sequence than the *B. glabrata* probe/reference sequence was
232 discarded as a putative paralog. After orthology filtering, probe regions of each locus were again aligned
233 with mafft using default parameters. Isoforms assembled by Bridger were collapsed with FASconCAT-
234 Gv1.04 (Kück & Longo, 2014) using IUPAC DNA ambiguity codes and retained downstream instead of
235 attempting to phase haplotypes. As only probe region sequences were subjected to orthology filtering,
236 we used USEARCH to reassemble head and tail regions with probe regions that passed filtering. The
237 resulting sequences were split by locus and aligned for a final time with mafft using the flags --

238 adjustdirectionaccurately, --allowshift, --unalignlevel 0.8 --leavegappyregion, and --globalpair. The --
 239 allowshift and --unalignlevel flags allowed for using a variable scoring matrix to control the risk of over-
 240 alignment in this step (see Katoh & Standley, 2016). Initially, all resulting alignments were inspected by
 241 eye. This revealed a handful of loci with large (>50 bp) insertions for a small number of individuals (~1-
 242 2). These insertions appeared to be assembly errors as they often matched another section of the
 243 alignment. We removed these alignment positions by removing any alignment column that had less than
 244 five non-gap characters, following common practice for phylogenomic datasets (e.g., Kocot, Poustka,
 245 Stöger, Halanych, & Schrödel, 2020; Whelan et al., 2017). We also removed the individuals used in probe
 246 set generation because reference sequences used in probe design did not include flanking regions and
 247 because each reference species was also sequenced using the probe set.

248 After initial assembly of phylogenetic datasets, putative paralogs and contamination were
 249 screened with the blast-based method in TreSpEx, using the packaged *Bos taurus* Linnaeus, 1758 and
 250 *Lottia gigantea* Sowerby, 1834 blast databases following Struck (2014) and Whelan et al. (2015). This
 251 method requires gene trees for each locus, and gene tree inference was done by inferring best-fit
 252 substitution models with Bayesian information criteria using ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy, Minh,
 253 Wong, Haeseler, & Jermin, 2017) and inferring the maximum likelihood tree with IQ-TREE 1.6.10
 254 (Nguyen, Schmidt, von Haeseler, & Minh, 2015) using the best-fit substitution models and other
 255 parameters set to defaults; 1000 ultrafast bootstrap replicates were performed to assess nodal support
 256 (Hoang, Chernomor, Von Haeseler, Minh, & Vinh, 2017). TreSpEx was also used to identify loci that may
 257 cause long branch attraction by calculating branch length heterogeneity scores (LB) for each locus.
 258 Density plots of LB heterogeneity and upper-quartile LB for each locus were plotted in R (Team, 2020)
 259 (Figs. S1-S3), and outlier loci were removed following Struck (2014) and Whelan et al. (2015). Base
 260 compositional heterogeneity of each locus was measured by calculating relative composition frequency
 261 variability (RCFV; Zhong et al., 2011) with BaCoCa (Kück & Struck, 2014). As above, density plots of RCFV
 262 values were plotted with R (Figs. S1-S3). As base compositional heterogeneity is a violation of most
 263 substitution models, outliers were removed from each dataset. This resulted in three datasets trimmed
 264 of putative paralogs and loci most likely to cause systematic error in downstream analyses.

265 266 *Phylogenetic dataset characteristics*

267 The dataset pleurocerid_full was larger than pleurocerid_masked as aliscore and alicut
 268 identified a high number of sites with alignment uncertainty in the probe flanking regions. However,
 269 more LB score outlier loci were identified in dataset pleurocerid_full, likely from poorly aligned sites
 270 causing long branches. Thus, dataset pleurocerid_full had more characters but less loci than the
 271 pleurocerid_masked dataset. Similarly, dataset pleurocerid_probe had the most loci but fewest
 272 characters. Taxon occupancy per locus was approximately 97% for each dataset. Overall missing data,
 273 including alignment gaps, ranged from 3.15%-17.14%. The pleurocerid_probe dataset had much less
 274 missing data because there were far fewer alignment gaps in the probe regions. This was expected as
 275 many of the flanking regions are likely not exons.

276 For datasets pleurocerid_masked and pleurocerid_full, visual inspection of alignments revealed
 277 that some alignment positions that flanked the probe region has a high amount of variability or a few
 278 taxa with seemingly divergent sequences. This sequence variation may represent misassembly, low
 279 quality alignments, or real genetic variation. We were unable to conclude with certainty the cause of
 280 this variation, but it was neither common nor isolated to specific taxa across loci. Given the large size of
 281 the dataset, we determined that any noise introduced by this variation would likely be less problematic
 282 for accurate phylogenetic inference than trying to trim a small number of sequences based on subjective
 283 judgement calls about which alignment positions or taxa warranted additional trimming.

284 **References**

- 285 Breinholt, JW, Earl, C, Lemmon, AR, Lemmon, EM, Xiao, L, & Kawahara, AY. (2018). Resolving
286 relationships among the megadiverse butterflies and moths with a novel pipeline for anchored
287 phylogenomics. *Systematic Biology*, **67**, 78-93. doi: 10.1093/sysbio/syx048
- 288 Burch, JB, & Tottenham, J. (1980). North American freshwater snails, species list, ranges, and
289 illustrations. *Walkerana*, **1**, 1-215. doi:
290 [http://molluskconservation.org/PUBLICATIONS/WALKERANA/Vol1/walkerana%20vol1%20no3%](http://molluskconservation.org/PUBLICATIONS/WALKERANA/Vol1/walkerana%20vol1%20no3%2081-216.PDF)
291 [2081-216.PDF](http://molluskconservation.org/PUBLICATIONS/WALKERANA/Vol1/walkerana%20vol1%20no3%2081-216.PDF)
- 292 Camacho, C, Coulouris, G, Avagyan, V, Ma, N, Papadopoulos, J, Bealer, K, & Madden, TL. (2009). BLAST+:
293 architecture and applications. *BMC Bioinformatics*, **10**, 421. doi: 10.1186/1471-2105-10-421
- 294 Chang, Z, Li, G, Liu, J, Zhang, Y, Ashby, C, Liu, D, . . . Huang, X. (2015). Bridger: a new framework for *de*
295 *novo* transcriptome assembly using RNA-seq data. *Genome Biology*, **16**, 30. doi:
296 10.1186/s13059-015-0596-2
- 297 Espeland, M, Breinholt, JW, Willmott, KR, Warren, AD, Vila, R, Toussain, AFA, . . . Kawahara, AY. (2018). A
298 comprehensive and dated phylogenomic analysis of butterflies. *Current Biology*, **28**, 770-
299 778.e775. doi: 10.1016/j.cub.2018.01.061
- 300 Fukuda, H, Haga, T, & Tataru, Y. (2008). *Niku-nuki*: a useful method for anatomical and DNA studies on
301 shell-bearing molluscs. *Zoosymposia*, **1**, 15-38. doi: 10.11646/zoosymposia.1.1.5
- 302 Goodrich, C. (1940). The Pleuroceridae of the Ohio River drainage system. *Occasional Papers of the*
303 *Museum of Zoology*, **417**, 1-21.
- 304 Hoang, DT, Chernomor, O, Von Haeseler, A, Minh, BQ, & Vinh, LS. (2017). UFBoot2: improving the
305 ultrafast bootstrap approximation. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, **35**, 518-522. doi:
306 10.1093/molbev/msx281
- 307 Johnson, PD, Bogan, AE, Brown, KM, Burkhead, NM, Cordeiro, JR, Garner, JT, . . . Strong, EE. (2013).
308 Conservation status of freshwater gastropods of Canada and the United States. *Fisheries*, **38**,
309 247-282. doi: 10.1080/03632415.2013.785396
- 310 Kalyanamoorthy, S, Minh, BQ, Wong, TKF, Haeseler, Av, & Jermini, LS. (2017). ModelFinder: fast model
311 selection for accurate phylogenetic estimates. *Nature Methods*, **14**, 587-589. doi:
312 10.1038/nmeth.4285
- 313 Katoh, K, & Standley, DM. (2013). MAFFT multiple sequence alignment software version 7:
314 improvements in performance and usability. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, **30**, 772-780. doi:
315 10.1093/molbev/mst010
- 316 Katoh, K, & Standley, DM. (2016). A simple method to control over-alignment in the MAFFT multiple
317 sequence alignment program. *Bioinformatics*, **31**, 1933-1942. doi:
318 10.1093/bioinformatics/btw108
- 319 Kocot, KM, Poustka, AJ, Stöger, I, Halanych, KM, & Schrödel, M. (2020). New data from Monoplacophora
320 and a carefully-curated dataset resolve molluscan relationships. *Scientific Reports*, **10**, 101. doi:
321 10.1038/s41598-019-56728-w
- 322 Kück, P, & Longo, GC. (2014). FASconCAT-G: extensive functions for multiple sequence alignment
323 preparations concerning phylogenetic studies. *Frontiers in Zoology*, **11**, 81. doi: 10.1186/s12983-
324 014-0081-x
- 325 Kück, P, & Struck, TH. (2014). BaCoCa - A heuristic software tool for the parallel assessment of sequence
326 biases in hundreds of gene and taxon partitions. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, **70**, 94-
327 98. doi: 10.1016/j.ympev.2013.09.011
- 328 Nguyen, L-T, Schmidt, HA, von Haeseler, A, & Minh, BQ. (2015). IQ-TREE: a fast and effective stochastic
329 algorithm for estimating maximum-likelihood phylogenies. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, **32**,
330 268-274. doi: 10.1093/molbev/msu300

- 331 Ó Foighil, D, Lee, T, Campbell, DC, & Clark, SA. (2009). All voucher specimens are not created equal: a
332 cautionary tale involving North American pleuroerid gastropods. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*,
333 **75**, 305-306. doi: 10.1093/mollus/eyp033
- 334 R Core Development Team. (2020). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. Vienna,
335 Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Retrieved from <http://www.R-project.org>
- 336 Struck, TH. (2014). TreSpEx—detection of misleading signal in phylogenetic reconstructions based on
337 tree information. *Evolutionary Bioinformatics*, **10**, 51-67. doi: 10.4137/EBO.S14239
- 338 Tryon, GW. (1873). *Land and fresh-water shells of North America part IV. Streptomatidae (American*
339 *melanians)*. Washington: Smithsonian Institution.
- 340 Whelan, NV, Johnson, PD, & Harris, PM. (2015). Life-history traits and shell morphology in the genus
341 *Leptoxis* Rafinesque, 1819 (Gastropoda: Cerithioidea: Pleuroceridae). *Journal of Molluscan*
342 *Studies*, **81**, 85-95. doi: 10.1093/mollus/eyu058
- 343 Whelan, NV, Kocot, KM, Moroz, LL, & Halanych, KM. (2015). Error, signal, and the placement of
344 Ctenophora sister to all other animals. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, **112**,
345 5773-2778. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1503453112
- 346 Whelan, NV, Kocot, KM, Moroz, TP, Mukherjee, K, Williams, P, Paulay, G, . . . Halanych, KM. (2017).
347 Ctenophore relationships and their placement as the sister group to all other animals. *Nature*
348 *Ecology & Evolution*, **1**, 1737-1746. doi: 10.1038/s41559-017-0331-3
- 349 Whelan, NV, & Strong, EE. (2016). Morphology, molecules and taxonomy: extreme incongruence in
350 pleurocerids (Gastropoda, Cerithioidea, Pleuroceridae) *Zoologica Scripta*, **45**, 62-87. doi:
351 10.1111/zsc.12139
- 352 Zhong, M, Hansen, B, Nesnidal, M, Golombek, A, Halanych, KM, & Struck, TH. (2011). Detecting the
353 symplesiomorphy trap: a multigene phylogenetic analysis of terebelliform annelids. *BMC*
354 *Evolutionary Biology*, **11**, 369. doi: 10.1186/1471-2148-11-369
- 355

Species	SRA	USNM	Collection Locality	Major drainage	Lat	Long	Assembled Loci	Raw paired-end Reads
<i>Athearnia anthonyi</i>		1597544	Limestone Creek	Tennessee River	34.6754	-86.8788	619	1,316,087
<i>Athearnia anthonyi</i>		1597545	Limestone Creek	Tennessee River	34.6754	-86.8788	455	566,532
<i>Elimia aff. acutocarinata</i>		1597548	Turkey Creek	Tennessee River	35.8901	-84.1490	623	1,406,643
<i>Elimia ampla</i>		1597552	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.0186	-87.0780	624	2,665,934
<i>Elimia ampla</i>		1597553	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.0186	-87.0780	626	1,873,273
<i>Elimia annettae</i>		1597555	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.0948	-87.0568	622	1,839,241
<i>Elimia annettae</i>		1597556	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.0948	-87.0568	626	1,538,676
<i>Elimia arachnoidea</i>		1597558	Steek Creek	Turkey Creek, Tennessee River	35.7207	-84.3484	623	1,735,951
<i>Elimia arachnoidea</i>		1597560	Steek Creek	Turkey Creek, Tennessee River	35.7207	-84.3484	622	1,446,293
<i>Elimia bellacrenata</i>		1597566	Unnamed Spring	Cahaba River	33.1673	-86.8135	620	1,519,855
<i>Elimia bellacrenata</i>		1597567	Unnamed Spring	Cahaba River	33.1673	-86.8135	406	299,124
<i>Elimia annae</i>		1597569	Bottle Creek	Conecuh River	31.2930	-86.7777	623	2,138,638
<i>Elimia carinocostata</i>		1597573	Brushy Creek	Black Warrior River	34.3306	-87.2855	334	298,680
<i>Elimia capillaris</i>		1597574	Big Canoe Creek	Coosa River	33.8871	-86.1972	624	1,035,777
<i>Elimia capillaris</i>		1597575	Big Canoe Creek	Coosa River	33.8871	-86.1972	619	1,408,272
<i>Elimia carinifera</i>		1597577	Crawfish Springs	South Chickamauga Creek, Tennessee River	34.8708	-85.2929	624	1,031,675
<i>Elimia godwini</i>		1597579	Ohatchie Creek	Coosa River	33.7795	-86.0002	617	1,122,345
<i>Elimia godwini</i>		1597580	Ohatchie Creek	Coosa River	33.7795	-86.0002	625	1,705,669
<i>Elimia carinifera</i>		1597581	Spring Creek	Coosa River	34.3228	-85.5875	471	500,374
<i>Elimia clenchi</i>		1597582	Choctawhatchee River	Gulf of Mexico	31.3431	-85.6112	624	1,946,392
<i>Elimia clenchi</i>		1597583	Choctawhatchee River	Gulf of Mexico	31.3431	-85.6112	621	1,941,768
<i>Elimia buffyae</i>		1597584	Choctawhatchee River	Gulf of Mexico	31.3431	-85.6112	614	1,246,471
<i>Elimia buffyae</i>		1597585	Choctawhatchee River	Gulf of Mexico	31.3431	-85.6112	326	217,022
<i>Elimia chrysti</i>		1597586	Hiwassee River	Tennessee River	35.2234	-84.5270	625	1,323,821
<i>Elimia chrysti</i>		1597587	Hiwassee River	Tennessee River	35.2234	-84.5270	623	1,315,184
<i>Elimia clavaeformis</i>		1597591	Turkey Creek	Tennessee River	35.8901	-84.1490	574	720,238
<i>Elimia clavaeformis</i>		1597594	Steek Creek	Tennessee River	35.7207	-84.3484	623	1,807,608
<i>Elimia showalteri</i>		1597595	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.0948	-87.0568	622	1,790,468
<i>Elimia cochliaris</i>		1597596	Unnamed Spring	Cahaba River	33.0569	-86.9670	619	1,698,270
<i>Elimia curreyana</i>		1597604	Barren River	Green River	36.6951	-86.0463	624	1,232,432
<i>Elimia curreyana</i>		1597605	Barren River	Green River	36.6951	-86.0463	624	1,176,023
<i>Elimia cylindracea</i>		1597609	Sucarnooche River	Black Warrior River	32.6119	-88.3491	619	2,462,892
<i>Elimia fascians</i>		1597610	Choccolocco Creek	Coosa River	33.5444	-86.0413	623	1,617,908
<i>Elimia fascians</i>		1597611	Choccolocco Creek	Coosa River	33.5444	-86.0413	625	2,258,444
<i>Elimia glarea</i>		1597613	Flat Creek	Choctawhatchee River	31.1092	-86.1461	623	3,391,995
<i>Elimia glarea</i>		1597614	Flat Creek	Choctawhatchee River	31.1092	-86.1461	623	2,650,058
<i>Elimia floridensis</i>		1597616	Juniper Spring Run	St. John's River	29.2131	-81.6547	612	940,245
<i>Elimia floridensis</i>		1597619	Alexander Spring	St. John's River	29.0817	-81.5767	621	1,655,905
<i>Elimia flava</i>		1597622	Chewacla Creek	Tallapoosa River	32.5360	-85.4966	618	1,755,408
<i>Elimia flava</i>		1597623	Chewacla Creek	Tallapoosa River	32.5360	-85.4966	622	1,505,459
<i>Elimia godwini</i>		1597627	Cane Creek	Coosa River	33.7291	-85.9637	624	1,721,845
<i>Elimia modesta</i>		1597630	Ohatchie Creek	Coosa River	33.7795	-86.0002	624	1,539,316
<i>Elimia modesta</i>		1597631	Ohatchie Creek	Coosa River	33.7795	-86.0002	626	1,949,718
<i>Elimia hydeii</i>		1597635	Locust Fork	Black Warrior River	33.8920	-86.6928	622	1,724,540
<i>Elimia hydeii</i>		1597637	Black Warrior River	Tombigbee	32.5623	-87.7447	565	679,310
<i>Elimia semicarinata</i>		1597638	Middle Fork Vermillion River	Wabash River	40.2384	-87.7743	623	1,087,110
<i>Elimia semicarinata</i>		1597639	Middle Fork Vermillion River	Wabash River	40.2384	-87.7743	614	573,872
<i>Elimia lachryma</i>		1597642	Coosa River	Alabama River	33.3746	-86.3568	623	1,825,792
<i>Elimia lachryma †</i>		1597644	Alabama River	Mobile River	32.3099	-86.7971	14	148,137
<i>Elimia olivula</i>		1597652	Cahaba River	Alabama River	32.6641	-87.2407	530	359,001
<i>Elimia olivula</i>		1597653	Cahaba River	Alabama River	32.6641	-87.2407	625	1,898,189
<i>Elimia potosiensis</i>		1597657	North Fork of the White River	White River, Western Mississippi River drainage	36.6424	-92.2200	620	2,120,910
<i>Elimia potosiensis</i>		1597658	North Fork of the White River	White River, Western Mississippi River drainage	36.6424	-92.2200	625	1,861,469
<i>Elimia pybasii</i>		1597667	Big Swann Creek	Duck River	35.7562	-87.4145	622	1,971,524
<i>Elimia pybasii</i>		1597668	Big Swann Creek	Duck River	35.7562	-87.4145	621	1,641,827
<i>Elimia laqueata</i>		1597684	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.7864	-87.4601	623	1,693,461
<i>Elimia annae</i>		1597696	Sepulga River	Conecuh River	31.2622	-86.7623	625	1,875,769
<i>Elimia showalteri</i>		1597699	Cahaba River	Alabama River	32.9483	-87.1407	624	1,752,252
<i>Elimia olivula</i>		1597700	Cahaba River	Alabama River	32.9483	-87.1407	625	1,724,117
<i>Elimia laqueata</i>		1597701	Harpeth River	Cumberland River	36.0543	-86.9287	621	2,082,248
<i>Elimia laqueata</i>		1597702	Harpeth River	Cumberland River	36.0543	-86.9287	622	1,025,298
<i>Elimia simplex</i>		1597710	Little Sycamore Creek	Big Sycamore Creek, Norris Lake/Clinch River	36.4606	-83.4932	622	1,615,994
<i>Elimia simplex</i>		1597711	Little Sycamore Creek	Big Sycamore Creek, Norris Lake/Clinch River	36.4606	-83.4932	623	1,537,431
<i>Elimia sp. Sipseys R.</i>		1597713	Sipseys River	Tombigbee	33.1031	-87.9504	624	1,604,585
<i>Elimia sp. Sipseys R.</i>		1597714	Sipseys River	Tombigbee	33.1031	-87.9504	622	2,182,833
<i>Elimia interveniens</i>		1597715	Limestone Creek	Tennessee River	34.6754	-86.8788	625	3,015,603
<i>Elimia interveniens</i>		1597717	Limestone Creek	Tennessee River	34.6754	-86.8788	602	1,505,281
<i>Elimia interveniens</i>		1597718	Little Duck River	Duck River	35.4869	-86.0917	622	1,939,222
<i>Elimia vanuxemiana</i>		1597734	Coosa River	Alabama River	33.3746	-86.3568	627	2,038,450
<i>Elimia vanuxemiana</i>		1597735	Coosa River	Alabama River	33.3746	-86.3568	625	1,523,867
<i>Elimia fluvialis</i>		1597739	Clinch River	Tennessee River	36.5664	-83.0417	622	1,643,311
<i>Elimia fluvialis</i>		1597740	Clinch River	Tennessee River	36.5664	-83.0417	608	1,275,937
<i>Leptoxis ampla</i>		1597741	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.2845	-86.8826	621	1,453,631
<i>Leptoxis arkansensis</i>		1597742	North Fork of the White River	White River, Western Mississippi River drainage	36.6424	-92.2200	621	2,031,776
<i>Leptoxis arkansensis</i>		1597743	North Fork of the White River	White River, Western Mississippi River drainage	36.6424	-92.2200	623	1,608,998
<i>Leptoxis compacta</i>		1597748	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.2845	-86.8826	617	913,406
<i>Leptoxis compacta</i>		1597749	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.2845	-86.8826	624	1,247,970
<i>Leptoxis foremani</i>		1597753	Oostanula River	Coosa River	34.4033	-85.097	621	2,286,382
<i>Leptoxis foremani</i>		1597754	Oostanula River	Coosa River	34.4033	-85.097	609	973,058
<i>Lithasia fuliginosa</i>		1597765	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.7864	-87.4601	621	1,461,814
<i>Lithasia aff. fuliginosa</i> , E. Frk Stones R.		1597766	East Fork Stones River	Stones River	35.9416	-86.3771	624	2,274,146
<i>Lithasia aff. fuliginosa</i> , Harpeth & Red R.		1597769	Harpeth River	Cumberland River	36.0880	-87.0245	624	1,841,150
<i>Lithasia aff. fuliginosa</i> , Harpeth & Red R.		1597771	Red River	Cumberland River	36.5885	-87.0889	623	1,965,277
<i>Lithasia geniculata</i>		1597776	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.9320	-87.7476	621	3,721,708
<i>Lithasia geniculata</i>		1597778	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.7864	-87.4601	624	2,171,091
<i>Lithasia duttoniana</i>		1597782	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.7864	-87.4601	623	1,993,395
<i>Lithasia fuliginosa</i>		1597783	Little Duck River	Tennessee River	35.4869	-86.0917	623	1,706,229
<i>Lithasia pinguis</i>		1597784	Little Duck River	Tennessee River	35.4869	-86.0917	622	2,040,236
<i>Lithasia pinguis</i>		1597787	Barren River	Caney Fork, Cumberland River	35.6740	-85.7767	614	1,435,102
<i>Lithasia verrucosa</i>		1597790	Sequatchie River	Tennessee River	35.1105	-85.5266	619	751,040
<i>Lithasia verrucosa</i>		1597791	Sequatchie River	Tennessee River	35.1105	-85.5266	624	1,273,969
<i>Lithasia lima</i>		1597793	Elk River	Tennessee River	35.0004	-87.0023	615	1,003,501
<i>Lithasia lima</i>		1597794	Elk River	Tennessee River	35.0004	-87.0023	617	1,310,829
<i>Leptoxis picta</i>		1597795	Alabama River	Mobile River	32.3166	-86.7901	608	679,484
<i>Leptoxis picta</i>		1597796	Alabama River	Mobile River	32.3166	-86.7901	604	972,931
<i>Leptoxis plicata</i>		1597798	Locust Fork	Black Warrior River	33.8892	-86.6950	611	1,028,334
<i>Leptoxis plicata †</i>		1597799	Locust Fork	Black Warrior River	33.8892	-86.6950	24	65,119
<i>Leptoxis aff. praerosa</i> Duck & Harpeth R.		1597800	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.9320	-87.7476	619	1,874,627
<i>Leptoxis aff. praerosa</i> Duck & Harpeth R.		1597805	Harpeth River	Tennessee River	36.0540	-86.9285	620	1,616,965
<i>Leptoxis aff. praerosa</i> Limestone Creek		1597807	Limestone Creek	Tennessee River	34.6754	-86.8788	615	999,577
<i>Leptoxis aff. praerosa</i> Duck & Harpeth R.		1597821	Buffalo River	Duck River	35.7844	-87.7740	620	1,759,967
<i>Leptoxis coosaensis</i>		1597823	Choccolocco Creek	Coosa River	33.5444	-86.0413	617	959,619
<i>Leptoxis coosaensis</i>		1597826	Ohatchie Creek	Coosa River	33.7795	-86.0002	604	1,162,984
<i>Leptoxis umbilicata</i>		1597827	Smith Fork	Caney Fork	36.1250	-85.8687	617	1,842,260

<i>Leptoxis umbilicata</i>	1597831	East Fork Stones River	Stones River	35.8291	-86.1793	580	968,596
<i>Leptoxis subglobosa</i>	1597835	Clinch River	Tennessee River	36.5664	-83.0417	620	1,217,964
<i>Leptoxis virgata</i>	1597837	Squatchie River	Tennessee River	35.1105	-85.5266	619	1,355,935
<i>Leptoxis virgata</i>	1597846	Nolichucky River	French Broad	36.0701	-82.9669	604	858,380
<i>Pleurocera aff. acuta</i> Rock R.	1597848	Rock River	Rock River	42.4492	-89.0596	622	1,211,688
<i>Pleurocera aff. acuta</i> Salt Frk. Vermillion R.	1597849	Salt Fork Vermillion River	Wabash River	40.0911	-87.8133	623	721,877
<i>Pleurocera aff. acuta</i> N. Frk. White R.	1597853	North Fork of the White River	White River, Western Mississippi River drainage	36.6424	-92.2200	624	1,375,906
<i>Pleurocera aff. acuta</i> N. Frk. White R.	1597854	North Fork of the White River	White River, Western Mississippi River drainage	36.6424	-92.2200	613	896,304
<i>Pleurocera alveare</i>	1597855	Squatchie River	Tennessee River	35.1105	-85.5266	623	1,568,044
<i>Pleurocera alveare</i>	1597856	Squatchie River	Tennessee River	35.1105	-85.5266	618	1,434,334
<i>Pleurocera aff. alveare</i>	1597858	Red River	Cumberland River	36.5885	-87.0889	587	805,854
<i>Pleurocera aff. alveare</i>	1597859	Red River	Cumberland River	36.5885	-87.0889	621	2,410,037
<i>Pleurocera annulifera</i>	1597861	Black Warrior River	Tombigbee River	32.6119	-88.3491	621	2,292,881
<i>Pleurocera annulifera</i>	1597863	Locust Fork	Black Warrior River	33.8920	-86.6928	625	2,235,982
<i>Pleurocera attenuata</i>	1597865	Crawfish Springs	West Chickamauga Creek	34.8708	-85.2929	625	1,295,676
<i>Pleurocera attenuata</i>	1597866	Crawfish Springs	West Chickamauga Creek	34.8708	-85.2929	623	1,393,365
<i>Pleurocera</i> sp. Duck & Buffalo R.	1597869	Buffalo River	Tennessee River	35.7844	-87.7740	622	1,581,366
<i>Pleurocera</i> sp. Buffalo R.	1597870	Buffalo River	Tennessee River	35.7844	-87.7740	622	1,781,478
<i>Pleurocera foremani</i>	1597872	Yellowleaf Creek	Coosa River	33.2602	-86.4510	621	1,252,585
<i>Pleurocera foremani</i>	1597873	Yellowleaf Creek	Coosa River	33.2602	-86.4510	624	1,202,776
<i>Pleurocera aff. prasinata</i>	1597875	Cahaba River	Alabama River	32.9464	-87.1404	618	972,438
<i>Pleurocera aff. prasinata</i>	1597876	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.2845	-86.8826	609	725,071
<i>Pleurocera walkeri</i>	1597902	Hiwassee River	Tennessee River	35.2234	-84.5270	620	1,130,914
<i>Pleurocera walkeri</i>	1597903	Hiwassee River	Tennessee River	35.2234	-84.5270	591	874,377
<i>Pleurocera</i> sp. Harpeth R. & Smith Frk.	1597904	Harpeth River	Cumberland River	36.0543	-86.9287	623	2,193,367
<i>Pleurocera</i> sp. Harpeth R. & Smith Frk.	1597905	Harpeth River	Cumberland River	36.0543	-86.9287	624	2,045,744
<i>Pleurocera prasinata</i>	1597908	Ohatchie Creek	Coosa River	33.7795	-86.0002	615	1,012,050
<i>Pleurocera</i> sp. Harpeth R. & Smith Frk.	1597912	Smith Fork	Caney Fork	36.1250	-85.8687	620	1,813,195
<i>Pleurocera</i> sp. Harpeth R. & Smith Frk.	1597914	Smith Fork	Caney Fork	36.1250	-85.8687	623	2,230,071
<i>Pleurocera</i> sp. Duck & Buffalo R.	1597915	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.7864	-87.4601	624	1,885,303
<i>Pleurocera</i> sp. Duck & Buffalo R.	1597916	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.7864	-87.4601	617	1,579,623
<i>Pleurocera postelli</i>	1597928	Clinch River	Tennessee River	36.5664	-83.0417	625	1,303,749
<i>Lithasia pinguis</i>	1597932	Barren Fork	Caney Fork, Cumberland River	35.6740	-85.7767	623	2,192,070
<i>Pleuroceridae</i> sp.	1597935	Collins River	Caney Fork, Cumberland River	35.6758	-85.7085	602	579,098
<i>Elimia cylindracea</i>	1597939	Sucarnooche River	Black Warrior River	32.6119	-88.3491	622	2,209,051
<i>Elimia melanoides</i>	1597940	Tapawingo Spring	Black Warrior River	33.7164	-86.6731	562	1,071,757
<i>Elimia melanoides</i>	1597941	Tapawingo Spring	Black Warrior River	33.7164	-86.6731	622	2,116,790
<i>Elimia annettae</i>	1597942	Cahaba River	Alabama River	32.9483	-87.1407	622	2,015,222
<i>Juga Plificera</i>	1597944	Abernathy Creek	Columbia River	46.2263	-123.1478	577	730,069
<i>Juga Plificera</i>	1597945	Abernathy Creek	Columbia River	46.2263	-123.1478	292	280,132
<i>Lithasia duttoniana</i>	1597946	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.9320	-87.7476	618	2,637,494
<i>Lithasia duttoniana</i>	1597948	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.9320	-87.7476	623	1,638,071
<i>Pleurocera prasinata</i>	1597950	Coosa River	Coosa River	33.3704	-86.3538	616	1,978,764
<i>Pleurocera postelli</i>	1597951	Tennessee River	Tennessee River	35.7406	-84.3323	622	1,575,180
<i>Pleurocera postelli</i>	1597952	Tennessee River	Tennessee River	35.7406	-84.3323	624	2,024,913
<i>Pleurocera walkeri</i>	1597954	Nolichucky River	French Broad River	36.0701	-82.9669	626	1,397,939
<i>Elimia acutocarinata</i>	1638565	Pistol Creek	Tennessee River	35.7538	-83.9703	623	1,063,741
<i>Elimia aff. acutocarinata</i>	1638566	Town Creek	Tennessee River	35.8262	-84.2760	622	1,133,292
<i>Elimia aterina</i>	1638567	Unnamed Spring Run	Powell River	36.5983	-83.6683	620	1,357,736
<i>Elimia carinocostata</i>	1638568	Brushy Creek	Black Warrior River	34.3306	-87.2855	540	702,163
<i>Elimia aff. carinifera</i>	1638569	Tapawingo Spring	Black Warrior River	33.7164	-86.6731	621	1,925,494
<i>Elimia aff. clavaeformis</i>	1638570	Pistol Creek	Little Tennessee River	35.7538	-83.9703	622	1,613,294
<i>Elimia aff. clavaeformis</i>	1638571	Turkey Creek	Tennessee River	35.8901	-84.1490	587	893,391
<i>Elimia cochliaris</i>	1638572	Unnamed Spring	Cahaba River	33.0569	-86.9670	565	791,952
<i>Elimia crenatella</i>	1638574	Cheaha Creek	Coosa River	33.5289	-86.0422	564	369,165
<i>Elimia crenatella</i>	1638575	Cheaha Creek	Coosa River	33.5289	-86.0422	606	573,091
<i>Elimia porrecta</i>	1638576	Unnamed Spring Run	Powell River	36.5983	-83.6683	621	1,192,612
<i>Elimia edgariana</i>	1638577	Barren Fork	Caney Fork, Cumberland River	35.6740	-85.7767	572	590,631
<i>Elimia edgariana</i>	1638578	Collins River	Caney Fork, Cumberland River	35.6758	-85.7085	623	1,515,931
<i>Elimia aff. simplex</i>	1638579	Duck Creek	Clinch River	36.5029	-83.2347	621	1,540,651
<i>Elimia aff. simplex</i>	1638580	Duck Creek	Clinch River	36.5029	-83.2347	620	1,340,262
<i>Elimia interveniens</i>	1638581	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.5858	-86.7870	619	1,304,273
<i>Elimia</i> sp. Green R.	1638582	Green River	Buffalo River	35.3285	-87.7618	623	1,395,555
<i>Elimia</i> sp. Green R.	1638583	Green River	Buffalo River	35.3285	-87.7618	503	323,438
<i>Elimia</i> sp. Richland Creek	1638584	Richland Creek	Nolichucky River	36.1252	-82.8457	621	1,503,925
<i>Elimia</i> sp. Richland Creek	1638585	Richland Creek	Nolichucky River	36.1252	-82.8457	623	1,621,850
<i>Elimia</i> sp. Red R.	1638586	Red River	Cumberland River	36.5885	-87.0889	623	1,130,227
<i>Elimia</i> sp. Red R.	1638587	Red River	Cumberland River	36.5885	-87.0889	619	919,016
<i>Leptoxis ampla</i>	1638588	Cahaba River	Alabama River	33.1653	-87.0296	617	1,008,336
<i>Leptoxis carinata</i>	1638591	Roanoke River	Roanoke River	37.2443	-80.1437	591	1,369,079
<i>Leptoxis carinata</i>	1638592	Roanoke River	Roanoke River	37.2443	-80.1437	623	1,619,879
<i>Leptoxis dilatata</i>	1638593	North Fork Holston River	Holston River	36.8909	-81.7494	622	1,648,790
<i>Leptoxis dilatata</i>	1638594	Indian Creek	New River	37.5151	-80.7696	622	840,750
<i>Leptoxis subglobosa</i>	1638595	North Fork Holston River	Holston River	36.9170	-81.6092	619	2,172,784
<i>Lithasia bubala</i>	1638597	Buffalo River	Tennessee River	35.7844	-87.7740	622	1,582,018
<i>Lithasia bubala</i>	1638598	Buffalo River	Tennessee River	35.7844	-87.7740	622	1,944,320
<i>Lithasia jayana</i>	1638599	Smith Fork	Cumberland River	36.1250	-85.8697	622	3,829,792
<i>Lithasia jayana</i>	1638600	Smith Fork	Cumberland River	36.1250	-85.8697	618	2,328,834
<i>Lithasia obovata</i>	1638601	Ohio River	Ohio River	38.1928	-86.3428	622	1,314,458
<i>Lithasia obovata</i>	1638602	Ohio River	Ohio River	38.1928	-86.3428	621	914,135
<i>Pleuroceridae</i> sp.	1638603	Collins River	Caney Fork, Cumberland River	35.6758	-85.7085	621	1,162,717
<i>Leptoxis praerosa</i>	1638604	Blue River	Ohio River	38.2303	-86.2534	472	378,683
<i>Leptoxis subglobosa</i>	1638605	North Fork Holston River	Holston River	36.9170	-81.6092	620	1,240,042
<i>Leptoxis subglobosa</i>	1638606	North Fork Holston River	Holston River	36.8909	-81.7494	620	1,269,968
<i>Pleurocera prasinata</i>	1638608	Alabama River	Mobile River	31.5501	-87.5143	615	1,127,121
<i>Pleurocera prasinata</i>	1638609	Alabama River	Mobile River	31.5501	-87.5143	625	1,399,802
<i>Pleurocera pyrenella</i>	1638610	Limestone Creek	Tennessee River	34.6754	-86.8788	622	1,733,279
<i>Pleurocera pyrenella</i>	1638611	Limestone Creek	Tennessee River	34.6754	-86.8788	623	2,080,901
<i>Elimia aff. acutocarinata</i>	1638564	Turkey Creek	Tennessee River	35.8901	-84.1490	Transcriptome	41,321,408
<i>Elimia crenatella</i>	1638624	Cheaha Creek	Coosa River	33.5289	-86.0422	Transcriptome	38,344,812
<i>Leptoxis ampla</i>	1638590	Cahaba River	Alabama River	32.9583	-87.1398	Transcriptome	67,987,270
<i>Lithasia geniculata</i>	1638596	Duck River	Tennessee River	35.7854	-87.5612	Transcriptome	42,048,690
<i>Pleurocera prasinata</i>	1638607	Alabama River	Mobile River	31.5510	-87.5138	Transcriptome	40,509,317
<i>Leptoxis ampla</i>	1638589	Cahaba River	Alabama River	32.9583	-87.1398	See Supplementary Material	

†: Individuals not included in phylogenetic analyses because not enough loci were assembled.

Supplementary Figure S1: Plots of LB scores and RCFV for the pleurocerid_probe dataset. Shaded regions represent loci that were trimmed from dataset during loci filtering steps.

Supplementary Figure S2: Plots of LB scores and RCFV for the pleurocerid_full dataset. Shaded regions represent loci that were trimmed from dataset during loci filtering steps.

Supplementary Figure S3: Plots of LB scores and RCFV for the pleurocerid_masked dataset. Shaded regions represent loci that were trimmed from dataset during loci filtering steps.

Supplementary Figure S4: Maximum likelihood tree inferred for the pleurocerid dataset. Nodes are labelled with ultrafast bootstrap support values. Branch lengths are in substitutions per site. Major clades are labelled as referenced in the main text. Individuals are labelled with museum accession numbers; see Table S1 for details.

Supplementary Figure S6: Maximum likelihood tree inferred for the pleurocerid_full dataset. Nodes are labelled with ultrafast bootstrap support values. Branch lengths are in substitutions per site. Major clades are labelled as referenced in the main text. Individuals are labelled with museum accession numbers; see Table S1 for details.

0.02

Supplementary Figure S7: ASTRAL-III species tree inferred for the pleurocerid_full dataset without a taxon map. Branches are labelled with local posterior probability. Major clades are labelled as referenced in the main text. Individuals are labelled with museum accession numbers; see Table S1 for details. Branch lengths are in coalescent units. Tip branch lengths were not estimated by ASTRAL and were arbitrarily set to 0.15 for visualization purposes.

Supplementary Figure S8: ASTRAL-III species tree inferred for the pleurocerid_full dataset with a taxon map. Taxon assignments for each individual are in Table S1. Branches are labelled with local posterior probability. Major clades are labelled as referenced in the main text. Branch lengths are in coalescent units.

Supplementary Figure S9: Maximum likelihood tree inferred for the pleurocerid_masked dataset. Nodes are labelled with ultrafast bootstrap support values. Branch lengths are in substitutions per site. Major clades are labelled as referenced in the main text. Individuals are labelled with museum accession numbers; see Table S1 for details.

Supplementary Figure S11: ASTRAL-III species tree inferred for the pleurocerid_masked dataset with a taxon map. Taxon assignments for each individual (i.e., individuals represented by each tip) are in Table S1. Branches are labelled with local posterior probability. Major clades are labelled as referenced in the main text. Branch lengths are in coalescent units.

